

MALATE COMPLEX OF COPPER

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Malate complex of copper has been investigated by p_H titration method within the p_H range of 2 to 6. A neutral complex A_1 is formed at lower p_H due to the reaction of a copper ion and malic acid with the liberation of the two protons. The equilibrium constant of the reaction has been found to be 3.89×10^{-5} . This complex with increase in p_H dissociates into a H^+ ion and complex C_1^- , the dissociation constant being 4.74×10^{-6} .

Malate complex of copper was studied by Delsal (*J. chim. phys.*, 1938, 35, 314) and the existence of a complex was postulated from two sets of polarimetric measurements and by electrometric measurements.

Many metals form 1:1 complex with tartrate and citrate ligands. Similar 1:1 complexes are also expected with malate ligands. The two carboxyl groups and the hydroxyl groups in malate ligand are most probably involved in the formation of the complex, since the formation of a stable complex with the carboxyl groups only is not possible. The malate ligand would therefore occupy three co-ordination positions. One or three molecules of water would be present in the co-ordination in four or six co-ordination complex respectively. Four and six co-ordination complexes of a divalent metal ion (M^{2+}) with malate chelate may be represented by structures (A) and (B) respectively.

The water molecules in the above aquo-complexes would ionise to proton and the corresponding hydroxo-complexes at higher p_H . If the hydroxyl group of malate ligand would form a co-ordinate link with the metal ion without the liberation of a proton, the complex would have been (A_1) and (B_1) respectively without any charge.

These complexes would also ionise to proton and the corresponding hydroxo-complex at higher p_H . It is very probable that when the ligand would be attached to the metal ion, it would occupy three co-ordination positions. The formation of the complex (A) or (B) and (A₁) or (B₁) from the metal ion and the malic acid would result in simultaneous liberation of three and two protons respectively. If the complex formed is 1:1 type, it is possible to distinguish between complex (A) or (B) and (A₁) or (B₁) provided that n , the number of proton liberated per metallic ion in the solution, is accurately determined. Besides, the study of the variation of n with p_H would give further information about the 'hydroxo ion.'

The p_H -titration method applied in the study of citrate complexes of nickel and cadmium (Pattnaik and Pauli, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 673) would be equally suitable for the study of the malate complexes.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The chemicals used were Analar quality reagents. A solution (100 c.c.) of malic acid (0.01875 g. mol.) and potassium nitrate (0.25 g. mol.) was titrated against 0.1N-NaOH solution and p_H was measured after each addition by a Marconi p_H -meter. The results are graphically shown by curve (A) in Fig. 1. The results obtained in another experiment with exactly the same conditions as above except that 0.0125 g. mol. of copper sulphate was present, is shown in curve (B) in Fig. 1. The p_H of the system containing copper is always lower than the other system under similar conditions. The temperature in both the experiments was 25°.

D I S C U S S I O N

Let A and B be two points on curves (A) and (B) respectively intersected by the p_H axis. The reaction taking place at A due to the addition of sodium hydroxide is

neutralisation of malic acid and the formation of bimalate and malate ions. The reactions taking place at B are neutralisation of malic acid and the formation of the complex. The reaction can be represented by

where Cu^{2+} , H_2M , C and H^+ represent the copper ion, malic acid, the complex (charge, if any, is not shown) and hydrogen ion respectively. The equilibrium constant is given by equation (1:1) where the square brackets indicate molar concentration per litre.

FIG. 1

$$\frac{[\text{C}] \times [\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}] \times [\text{H}_2\text{M}]} = K \quad \dots (1:1)$$

Let $[\text{NaOH}]_A$, $[\text{M}]_A$, $[\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A$, $[\text{HM}^-]_A$ and $[\text{M}^{2-}]_A$ be respectively the concentration in g. mol. per litre of sodium hydroxide, total malate, malic acid, bimalate ion and malate ion. The concentrations at B are similarly expressed by $[\]_B$. The concentration of total copper at B is equal to that of copper sulphate and is represented by $[\text{CuSO}_4]$. The concentration of hydrogen ion is the same at both A and B and is represented by $[\text{H}^+]$.

$$[\text{NaOH}]_A + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{HM}^-]_A + 2[\text{M}^{2-}]_A \quad \dots \dots$$

$$= \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \cdot [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A + 2 \frac{k_1 \cdot k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \cdot [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A$$

where k_1 and k_2 are respectively the first and the second dissociation constant of malic acid ($k_1 = 5.5 \times 10^{-4}$; $k_2 = 2.1 \times 10^{-5}$; Cannan and Kibrick, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2314).

$$[\text{NaOH}]_A + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A \left(\frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + 2 \frac{k_1 \times k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \right)$$

or
$$[\text{NaOH}]_A + [\text{H}^+] = a [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where
$$a = \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + 2 \frac{k_1 \times k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2}.$$

Similarly

$$[\text{NaOH}]_B + [\text{H}^+] = n[\text{C}] + [\text{HM}^-]_B + 2[\text{M}^{2-}]_B$$

or
$$[\text{NaOH}]_B + [\text{H}^+] = n[\text{C}] + a[\text{H}_2\text{M}]_B \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Subtracting equation (2) from (3) one gets,

$$[\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A = n[\text{C}] + a([\text{H}_2\text{M}]_B - [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A)$$

or
$$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] = n[\text{C}] + a\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{M}] \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta[\text{NaOH}] = [\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A$ and $\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{M}] = [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_B - [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A$.

$$[\text{M}]_A = [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A + [\text{HM}^-]_A + [\text{M}^{2-}]_A$$

$$= [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A + [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2}$$

or
$$[\text{M}]_A = [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A \left(1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \right)$$

or
$$[\text{M}]_A = b[\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

where
$$b = 1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2}.$$

Similarly

$$[\text{M}]_B = [\text{C}] + [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_B + [\text{HM}^-]_B + [\text{M}^{2-}]_B$$

or
$$[\text{M}]_B = [\text{C}] + b[\text{H}_2\text{M}]_B \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Subtracting equation (5) from (6) one gets

$$[\text{M}]_B - [\text{M}]_A = [\text{C}] + b([\text{H}_2\text{M}]_B - [\text{H}_2\text{M}]_A)$$

or
$$\Delta[\text{M}] = [\text{C}] + b\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{M}] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta[\text{M}] = [\text{M}]_B - [\text{M}]_A$.

Substituting the value of $\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{M}]$ from equation (7) in equation (4) one gets

$$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] = n[\text{C}] + \frac{a}{b} (\Delta[\text{M}] - [\text{C}])$$

or
$$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[\text{M}] = [\text{C}] \times \left(n - \frac{a}{b} \right) \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

or
$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{M}]}{[\text{C}]} + \frac{a}{b} = n \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

when the formation of the complex is complete,

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{CuSO}_4]$$

Hence
$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{M}]}{[\text{CuSO}_4]} - \frac{a}{b} = n \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

All quantities in the above equation except n can be calculated from the experimental results at different p_H values; the values of n , thus calculated at different p_H values, are recorded in Table I. Below p_H 4, the value of n is less than 2 and above this p_H , n is > 2 and < 3 . A complex C, which is formed from copper ion and malic acid is in the process of formation at the lower p_H range. The concentration of this complex increases with increasing p_H and is very nearly complete at about p_H 4. Above p_H 4, the complex C dissociates like a monobasic acid which increases with increasing p_H . The reaction may be represented by

$$\frac{[H^+] \times [C_1^-]}{[C]} = K_1 \quad (11-1)$$

The equilibrium constant is given by equation (11-1).

Calculation of Equilibrium Constants

Below p_H 4 copper exists in solution partly as Cu^{2+} and partly as complex C. The complex C is formed with the liberation of two protons. Taking n to be 2 and substituting the values of $\Delta [NaOH]$, $\Delta [M]$ and a/b in equation (9), $[C]$ is calculated at different p_H values (below p_H 4). $[Cu^{2+}]$ is obtained by subtracting $[C]$ from $[CuSO_4]$. $[H_2M]_a$ is obtained from equation (4) or (6). The value of K , thus calculated and shown in the last column of Table I, is fairly constant and the mean value is 3.89×10^{-5} .

TABLE I

p_H .	$\Delta NaOH \times 10^1$.	$-\Delta [M] \times 10^3$.	$[CuSO_4] \times 10^3$.	n .	$[C] \times 10^3$.	$[H_2M]_a \times 10^3$.	$K \times 10^5$.
2.750	2.775	0.520	11.800	0.487	1.649	12.220	4.205
2.875	3.495	0.655	11.470	0.622	2.171	10.590	3.921
3.000	3.990	0.748	11.210	6.747	2.611	9.099	3.336
3.125	4.447	0.834	10.960	0.881	3.089	7.612	2.899
3.250	5.439	1.020	10.690	1.093	4.62	5.940	3.262
3.375	6.353	1.191	10.420	1.284	5.071	4.457	4.547
3.500	6.676	1.251	10.230	1.456	5.896	3.422	3.975
3.625	7.141	1.339	10.000	1.593	6.676	2.362	4.929
3.750	7.554	1.416	9.781	1.754	7.678		
3.875	7.969	1.494	9.594	1.916	8.835		
4.000	7.884	1.478	9.448	2.015	9.592		
4.125	8.230	1.543	9.260	2.174	11.040		
4.250	8.574	1.607	9.090	2.337	12.840		
4.375	8.504	1.594	8.973	2.440	14.370		
4.500	8.283	1.552	8.865	2.523	16.020		
4.625	8.345	1.564	8.742	2.648	18.770		
4.750	8.191	1.536	8.662	2.732	21.830		
4.875	8.160	1.531	8.590	2.832	26.340		
5.000	7.638	1.432	8.531	2.843	30.120		
5.125	7.300	1.369	8.504	2.867	35.810		
5.250	7.109	1.332	8.474	2.903	43.910		
5.375	6.916	1.296	8.445	2.930	54.640		

Above p_H 4, the concentration of copper ion is very small and, hence, neglected. Copper exists in solution partly as C and partly as C_1^- .

Hence $[C] + [C_1^-] = [CuSO_4]$... (12)

For each C and C_1^- formed, respectively two and three protons are liberated. Total acid liberated due to the formation of complex is equal $2[C] + 3[C_1^-]$.

Hence $n = \frac{2[C] + 3[C_1^-]}{[CuSO_4]}$

or $\frac{2([C] + [C_1^-])}{[CuSO_4]} + \frac{[C_1^-]}{[CuSO_4]} = n$,

Since $[C] + [C_1^-] = [CuSO_4]$

$\therefore 2 + \frac{[C_1^-]}{[CuSO_4]} = n$

or $[C_1^-]/[CuSO_4] = n - 2$... (13)

and $\frac{[C] + [C_1^-]}{[CuSO_4]} - \frac{[C_1^-]}{[CuSO_4]} = 1 - (n - 2)$

or $\frac{[C]}{[CuSO_4]} = 3 - n$... (14)

Instead of calculating the exact values of $[C]$ and $[C_1^-]$ for the determination of K_1 by equation (11.1) respectively the values of $[C]/[CuSO_4]$ and $[C_1^-]/[CuSO_4]$ can be substituted. K_1 thus obtained are shown in Table II. It is fairly constant and the mean value is 4.74×10^{-5} .

TABLE II

pH .	n .	$K_1 \times 10^5$.	pH .	n .	$K_1 \times 10^5$.
4.375	2.440	3.390	5.000	2.843	5.369
4.500	2.523	3.467	5.125	2.867	4.776
4.525	2.648	4.366	5.250	2.903	5.235
4.750	2.731	4.857	5.375	2.930	5.604
4.875	2.832	6.601			

Structure of the Complex.—The complex C has no charge. It is formed with liberation of two protons. The most probable structure is given by structure (A₁) since copper generally forms four co-ordination. The structure of complex C_1^- is given by either structure A (*vide supra*) or structure (A₂) given below depending on whether the proton is liberated from the hydroxyl group or water molecule in complex C.

